

TAQQOSLAMA TUSHUNCHASI VA UNING XOSSALARI.

Sharipova Madina Po'latovna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

"Umumtexnik fanlar" kafedrası o'qituvchisi

saripovamadina807.m@gmail.com

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Maqolada taqqoslash jarayonlarining maqsadi, obyektlar yoki jarayonlarning o'zaro bog'liqliklarini tushuntirib chiqish va buning natijasida ma'lumotlar olish, aniqlash o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Butun son, modul, taqqoslama, qoldiq, tengsizlik.

ANNOTATION.

Integer, modulus, comparison, remainder, inequality.

Taqqoslamalar o'zaro bog'liqlik va taqqoslash usullari boyicha har bir sohada o'zgartirib boriladi. Taqqoslashni to'g'ri amalga oshirish uchun, ma'lumotlar olish, tahlil qilish, natijalarni chiqarish lozim.

Bunday taqqoslamalarning umumiy ko'rinishi quyidagicha:

$$ax \equiv b \pmod{m} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda $a, b, -$ butun sonlar. Taqqoslamani yechish deganda uni to'g'ri sonli taqqoslamaga aylantiruvchi sonlar sinfini tushunamiz. Chunki (1) taqqoslamani biror x_1 son qanoatlantirsa, uni $x_1 + mt$ (t -butun son) sonlar sistemasi ham qanoatlantiradi. (1) taqqoslamani yechimini topish uchun biz quyidagi ikkita holni qaraymiz. Bitta sinfdagi barcha yechimlarini bitta yechim deb qabul qilamiz.

1. $(a, m) = 1$. Agar (1) taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lsa, u yechim m modul bo'yicha chegirmalarning birorta sinfidan iborat bo'ladi. Ma'lumki, chegirmalarning to'la sistemasidagi har bir chegirmaga bitta sinf mos kelardi. Demak, x o'zgaruvchi chegirmalarning to'la sistemasini qabul qilar ekan, u holda chiziqli forma haqidagi 1-teoremaga asosan ax ham chegirmalarning to'la sistemasini qabul qiladi.

x noma'lumning biror x_0 qiymatida ax_0 chegirma bilan b son bitta sinfga tegishli bo'ladi, ya'ni $ax_0 \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lib $x \equiv x_0 \pmod{m}$ (1) taqqoslamani yagona yechimi bo'ladi.

2. $(a, m) = d > 1$. Ma'lumki, $ax \equiv b \pmod{m}$ taqqoslamani $ax - b = my$ deb yozish mumkin. Bu yerda y - butun son.

Demak, $ax - b = my$ tenglikda $(m/d \wedge a/d) \Rightarrow b/d$. Bundan agar $b \times d$, ya'ni b son va d ga bo'linmasa, (1) taqqoslama yechimga ega bo'lmaydi; degan natija kelib chiqadi.

Faraz qilaylik, $b = db$ bo'lsin. taqqoslamalarning 5-xossasiga asosan (1) ning ikkala qismi va modulini d ga bo'lib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$a, x \equiv b_1 \pmod{m_1} \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda $(a_1, m_1) = 1$ bo'lganidang (1) holga asosan (2) taqqoslama m_1 modul bo'yicha yagona x_0 yechimga ega:

$$x \equiv x_0 \pmod{m_1} \Rightarrow x = x_0 + km_1, \quad k \in C.$$

Bu yechim (1) ni ham qanoatlantiradi. Lekin (1) ning yechimlari shu bilan tugallanmaydi. Burilgan taqqoslamaning yechimlarini m modul bo'yicha topish uchun quyidagilarga e'tibor beramiz:

$$\dots, x_1 - m_1, x_1, x_1 + m, \dots,$$

$$x_1 + (d-1)m_1, x_1 + dm_1, \dots \quad (3)$$

Bu chegirmalarning har biri m_1 modul bo'yicha teng qoldikli bo'lib, m modul bo'yicha har xil sinfga tegishlidir. Shu xil sinflarning vakillari

$$x_1, x_1 + m_1 + x_1 + 2m_2, \dots, x_1 + (d-1)m_1 \quad (4)$$

dan iborat. Haqiqatan ham (4) ning har qanday ikkitadan elementi m modul bo'yicha taqqoslanuvchi emas. (3) sinfnig (4) ga kirmagan har bir elementi uchun (4) dan shunday element topiladiki, ularning ayirmasi $m_1 d = m$ ga bo'linadi. Shuning uchun ular bitta sinfnig vakillari hisoblanadi. Demak, $(a, m) = d$ va $(b, m) = d$ bo'lsa, (1) taqqoslama (4) orqali aniqlanuvchi d ta yechimga ega ekan. Yuqoridagilarga asosan quyidagi xulosalarni yoza olamiz:

Xulosalar: 1. Agar $(a, m) = 1$ bo'lsa, (1) ning yechimi mavjud va yagonadir.

2. $(a, m) = d > 0$ bo'lib,

a) $a \times b$ chin bo'lsa, yechim mavjud emas;

v) a/b chin bo'lsa, (1) taqqoslama d ta yechimga ega.

Misollar. 1. $3x \equiv 7 \pmod{11}$; $(3, 11) = 1$ bo'lgani uchun yechim yagona bo'ladi. m modul bo'yicha chegirmalarning to'la sistemali $\{0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \pm 4, \pm 5\}$ dan iborat. Bevosita tekshirib ko'rish bilan $x \equiv -5 \pmod{11}$ yechim ekanligiga ishonch hosil qilamiz.

$$2. 5x \equiv 7 \pmod{15},$$

$(5, 15) = 5$, lekin 7×5 bo'lgani uchun bu taqqoslama yechimga ega emas.

3. $9x \equiv 6 \pmod{15}$; $(9, 15) = 3$; $(6, 15) = 3$; bo'lgani uchun taqqoslama uchta yechimga ega bo'ladi. Haqiqatan taqqoslamani $2x \equiv 2 \pmod{5}$ shaklda yozib olamiz $(3, 5) = 1$ bo'lgani uchun bu taqqoslama 5 modul bo'yicha yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi. Haqiqatan,

$$x \equiv -1 \pmod{5}$$

yechimdir.

Berilgan taqqoslamaning yechimi $-1, -1+5, -1+10 \pmod{15}$ yoki $x \equiv -1 \pmod{5}, 4 \pmod{15}, 9 \pmod{15}$ dan iborat.

Bu yechim bilan birgalikda $-1, -1+5, -1+10 \pmod{15}$ yoki $x \equiv -1 \pmod{15}, 4 \pmod{15}, 9 \pmod{15}$ ham yechim bo'ladi.

a va b butun sonlarni butun musbat m soniga bo'lganda bir xil qoldiq qoladigan, ya'ni

$$a = mq_1 + r \quad \text{va} \quad b = mq_2 + r,$$

bo'lsa, a va b sonlar teng qoldiqdli yoki m modul bo'yicha o'zaro taqqoslanadigan sonlar deyiladi va quyidagicha yoziladi: $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$

" a son b bilan m modul bo'yicha taqqoslanadi" deb o'qiladi.

Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a - b$ ayirma m ga qoldiqsiz bo'linadi, va aksincha, agar a va b sonlarning ayirmasi m ga bo'linsa, u holda $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ o'rinli bo'ladi (*taqqoslamaning ma'nosi haqidagi teorema*).

Har qanday butun son m modul bo'yicha o'zining qoldig'i bilan taqqoslanadi, ya'ni, agar $a = mq + r$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv r \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.

Xususiyl holda, agar $r = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi; bu taqqoslama $m \mid a$ ekanligini, ya'ni m soni a ning bo'luvchisi ekanligini bildiradi, aksincha ham o'rinli, agar $m \mid a$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ deb yoziladi.

Taqqoslamalarning asosiy xossalari (tengliklarning xossalariga o'xshash)

1. Agar $a \equiv cs \pmod{m}$ va $b \equiv c \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.
2. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ va $c \equiv d \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \pm c \equiv b \pm d \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.
3. Agar $a + b \equiv c \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv c - b \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.
4. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \pm mk \equiv b \pmod{m}$, yoki $a \equiv b \pm mk \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.
5. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ va $c \equiv d \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $ac \equiv bd \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.
6. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a^n \equiv b^n \pmod{m}$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) bo'ladi.
7. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda ixtoriy k butun son uchun $ak \equiv bk \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.

8. Agar $ak \equiv bk \pmod{m}$ va $(k, m) = 1$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.

9. Agar $f(x) = a_0 x^n + a_1 x^{n-1} + \dots + a_n$ ($a_i \in \mathbb{Z}$) va $x \equiv x_1 \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $f(x) \equiv f(x_1) \pmod{m}$ bo'ladi.

Taqqoslamalarning maxsus xossalari

1. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ bo'lsa, u holda $k \in \mathbb{N}$ uchun $ak \equiv bk \pmod{mk}$ bo'ladi. 2.

Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m}$ va $a = a_1 d$, $b = b_1 d$, $m = m_1 d$ bo'lsa, u holda $a_1 \equiv b_1 \pmod{m_1}$ bo'ladi.

3. Agar $a \equiv b \pmod{m_1}$, $a \equiv b \pmod{m_2}$, ..., $a \equiv b \pmod{m_k}$ bo'lsa, u holda $a \equiv b \pmod{M}$ bo'ladi, bu yerda $M = [m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k]$.

4. Agar taqqoslama m modul bo'yicha o'rinli bo'lsa, u holda bu taqqoslama m ning ixtiyoriy bo'luvchisi bo'lgan d modul bo'yicha ham o'rinli bo'ladi.

5. Agar taqqoslamaning bir tomoni biror songa bo'linsa, u holda uning ikkinchi tomoni va moduli ham shu songa bo'linadi.

1-Misol. Quyidagi shartlarni taqqoslamalar yordamida yozing:

- 219 va 128 sonlarni 7 ga bo'lganda bir xil qoldiq qoladi;
- (-352) sonini 31 ga bo'linganida qoldiq 20 ga teng bo'ladi;
- $487 - 7$ ayirma 12 ga bo'linadi;
- 20 - soni 389 ni 41 ga bo'lgandagi qoldiqdan iborat;
- N soni juft;
- N soni toq;
- N sonining ko'rinishi $4k + 1$ dan iborat;
- N sonining ko'rinishi $10k + 3$ dan iborat;
- N sonining ko'rinishi $8k - 3$ dan iborat.

Yechilishi. Taqqoslamaning ma'nosi haqidagi teoremaga asosan:

- $219 \equiv 128 \pmod{7}$;
- $-352 \equiv 20 \pmod{31}$;
- $487 \equiv 7 \pmod{12}$;
- $389 \equiv 20 \pmod{41}$;
- $N \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$;
- $N \equiv 1$ yoki $-1 \pmod{2}$;
- $N \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$;
- $N \equiv 3 \pmod{10}$;
- $N \equiv -3 \pmod{8}$.

2-Misol. Quyidagi shartni qanoatlantiradigan m ning qiymatlarini toping:

$$20 \equiv 8 \pmod{m}.$$

Yechilishi. m ning qiymatlari (taqqoslamaning ma'nosi haqidagi teorema asosan) $20 - 8 = 12$ ning bo'luvchilaridan iborat, ya'ni: 1; 2; 3; 4; 6; 12.

3-Misol. $2^{5n} - 1$ ning 31 ga bo'linishini isbotlang ($n \in N$).

Yechilishi. $2^5 - 1 = 31$ bo'lganligi uchun $2^5 \equiv 1 \pmod{31}$. Bu taqqoslamaning ikkala tomonini (6-xossaga asosan) n darajaga ko'tarib,

$2^{5n} \equiv 1 \pmod{31}$ ni hosil qilamiz, bu esa $31 / (2^{5n} - 1)$ ni anglatadi.

4-Misol. 2^{100} sonining oxirgi ikkita raqamini toping.

Yechilishi. Berilgan sonning oxirgi ikki raqami bu sonni 100 ga bo'lganda hosil bo'ladigan qoldiqdan iborat. Demak, quyidagi taqqoslamani qanoatlantiradigan x sonini topish talab qilinadi:

$$2^{100} \equiv x \pmod{100}.$$

Ikkining kichik darajalaridan boshlab, 100 ga bo'lganda hosil bo'ladigan qoldiqlarni ketma-ket ajratamiz:

$$2^{100} = (2^{10})^{10} = (1024)^{10}; (1024)^{10} \equiv (24)^{10} \pmod{100}.$$

$$(24)^{10} = (576)^5 \equiv 76^5 \equiv (76)^4 \cdot 76 = (5776)^2 \cdot 76 \equiv (76)^2 \cdot 76 = 5776 \cdot 76 \equiv 76^2 \equiv 5776 \equiv 76 \pmod{100}.$$

Shunday qilib, 2^{100} sonining oxirgi ikki raqamir 7 va 6 dan iborat.

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